

Summary of advisory panel meetings throughout Step 1 of realist review

Meetings	Purpose	Recommendations & Outcomes
<p>Content Advisors Online meetings with PhD candidate and content advisors/ PhD supervisors. Monthly from September 2022 to April 2023</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Refining focus of realist review including aims and objectives Developing research questions Developing preliminary IPTs Planning training required Planning dissemination of findings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developed aims and objectives Developed review questions Developed preliminary IPTs Agreed on realist training that would be undertaken by YF Developed preliminary plan for dissemination of findings (peer reviewed journals and conferences)
<p>Content Advisors & Realist Advisors 2x online meetings with content advisors and realist advisors.</p> <p>Meeting 1 10th January, 2023 All members were in attendance</p> <p>Meeting 2 7th March, 2023 Apologies from CJ. All other members in attendance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning and agreeing collaborative process Review of research project with specific focus on realist review Recommendations from realist advisors for further development and refinement of critical elements including: research questions; IPTs 	<p>Meeting One</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plan for collaborative progress agreed (including meeting schedules, document sharing and feedback etc.) <p>Recommendations at meeting one included that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resource mechanisms be disaggregated from reasoning mechanisms in line with Dalkin et al., (2015) and that distal and proximal outcomes be considered when organising IPTs (Leutsch review et al., 2020) Review questions be revised and maintained at the forefront of thought throughout the course of the review and programme theory development <p>Meeting Two</p> <p>Agreed that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review questions were appropriate for realist enquiry Revised IPTs with overarching graphic representation were “good enough” to proceed and no amendments were requested Preliminary plan for dissemination of review findings agreed (e.g., peer review publications) and review protocols be prepared for registration on PROSPERO and publication on HRB Open Research YF would co-ordinate ongoing collaborations via email and schedule online meetings as necessary during the review process
<p>Medical Educationalist 28th February, 2023</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review IPTs to judge coherence and plausibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overviewed overarching IPT graphic and referenced narrative IPTs as required Recommended rephrasing of M1 in graphically represented IPT and YF changed to current phrasing

<p>1x 45 face to face minute meeting with medical educationalist, YF & RMcM</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advisor pointed out the “confidence “cited in M3 could also be classed as an outcome in a different CMOC. • Recommended increased transparency around evidence source for IPTs. Agreed that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sources for initial IPT be included. (See additional extended data-materials included in scoping exercise) ○ Sources will be transparent and explicitly referenced during middle range theory development process • Agreed IPT graphic was coherent and plausible. Advisor could clearly identify the most usual path medical students or medical practitioners would take along the box and arrow IPT graphic.
<p>PPI Advisors Consultation 1 21st & 28th March 2023 2 x 2 hour face to face meetings with advisor presenting with mild aphasia & YF Consultation 2 9th June 2023 1x 2.5 hour face to face meeting with YF and two advisors – person with severe aphasia and severe apraxia of speech and his spouse</p>	<p>Meetings 1 & 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview and explanation of realist review • Overview of requirements from advisors • Planning collaborative process • Review of IPTs with opportunity to recommend revisions • Reflecting on own experiences, advisors were asked to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Judge if IPTs were coherent and plausible, and ○ Recommend revisions as appropriate 	<p>Consultation 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreed collaborative process (including time frame, meeting schedule, information sharing and feedback process) • Reviewed narrative and graphic IPTs with detailed discussion around individual CMOCs and amalgamated theories • Advisor confirmed that he understood concepts • Advisor agreed that IPTs were coherent and logical and that the graphically presented overarching IPT captured the essence of what was entailed in becoming a skilled communication partner • Advisor emphasised that training health care professionals to communicate better with people with aphasia is of high importance. • Advisor stated that a willingness to engage with people with aphasia is one of the most important factors in achieving successful communication. (Ranking CMOCs was not a requirement, this may be relevant and returned to as programme theory development continues over the course of the review) • Contributor stated that IPTs did not require any amendments <p>Consultation 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreed collaborative process (including time frame, meeting schedule, information sharing and feedback process)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewed graphic IPTs with explanations from YF and reference to narrative presentation as required • Advisors confirmed that they understood concepts • Advisors stated that IPTs were coherent and logical • Spouse emphasised that narrative IPTs, specifically referencing involvement of people with stroke acquired communication difficulties in CPT (i.e., CMOCs #8 & #9), accurately captured this couple’s experiences. • Advisor with aphasia emphasised that participating with students on CPT was “very good”. • Neither advisor requested any changes.
<p>Student Advisors (Pre-registration SLTs) Meeting 1 13th April, 2023 1x 1 hr 15 min meeting with 3 advisors and YF</p> <p>Meeting 1 19th April, 2023 1x 1 hr 15 min meeting with 1 advisors and YF</p> <p>Note: Previously, when invited to advise on this review, these students (and some others who decided not to become advisors) attended a face to face meeting which focused on an explaining realist review and overviewing the commitment require from</p>	<p>Meetings 1 &2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of IPTs with opportunity to recommend revisions • Reflecting on own experiences, advisors were asked to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Judge if IPTs were coherent and plausible, and ○ Recommend revisions as appropriate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student advisors confirmed that they understood concepts and there were detailed discussions around individual CMOCs and amalgamated theories. • Agreed IPT graphic was very clear and accurately reflected their CPT experiences • It was highlighted that not all “negative emotions” reflect dissatisfaction with the programme. Some reflected growing appreciation of the impact of the underlying impairment and this should be more accurately reflected in the IPT narratives. Substituted “negative emotion” to “off putting” in outcome of CMOC #3. Recommended including the word “empathy” to ensure specific concepts were clearly articulated. YF revised IPTs – included “empathetic” in outcome of CMOC #8 • Requested that severity of communication impairment be considered during experiential learning. Too mild a presentation may impeded learning opportunities. YF amended narrative CMOC #6a to include the phrase “adequately challenging”.

student advisors on this project.		
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